

The Coupling Constant Series and the Feynman Diagrams

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Abstract:

By analyzing the new framework, 8T, and the insights gain regarding the nature of the electron as the majestic (3) in the coupling term describing the Electric, it is possible add an additional liar, a numerical analysis of the Feynman diagrams in an elegant fashion. Analysis of the diagrams on a varying Lorentz manifold , $s = (M, g_E)$ with signature (3,1), which is the connected Einstein manifold, $M = M_0 \times R$, invoked stationary, by the Euler Lagrange operator. The analysis of the diagrams will be done via the primordial coupling constant series, derived in March 2021.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Primes set} \quad (2.1)$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P} \quad (2.2)$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (2.3)$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ...$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

Examine the term describing the electric coupling. We proved majestic (3) is the electron in the 8-Theory thesis.

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + 5 \quad (2.31)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (2.32)$$

$$e \searrow \rightarrow (\gamma) \rightarrow e \nearrow \quad (2.33)$$

$$(+3) \rightarrow (\gamma) \rightarrow (+3) \quad (2.34)$$

$$(+3) \rightarrow (+5) \rightarrow (+3) \quad (2.35)$$

$$(+3) + N_V = (+3) + 5 = 8$$

$$8 = \text{even}$$

$$\text{even} = 0$$

The electron, represented as the majestic (3) combined with the net variation yielding an even amount of variation that vanish. That is synonymous with saying that the electron has absorbed the photon. The conservation of variation ensure that no electron can disappear from the manifold. However, as the combination of N_V and the electron, i.e. the (3) yielding an even, there has to be a vanishing of certain sort into the electron. It is moved into an excited state, vanishing of curvature, $(\gamma) = (+5)$ into the receiving electron, which causes the deflection in trajectory. Using the numerical trait and insight gained by the coupling constant series, by the 8T framework, it is possible to add an additional liar to the Feynman diagrams and interactions among bosons and fermions in what seems as a very simple and elegant manner.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)